

Assembly Theory part 2: the methodology correlates very poorly with abiotic chemical processes

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Assembly Theory aims to provide a unified and novel framework for understanding the interplay of physics, chemistry, and biology, bridging the divide between inert and living matter. Central to this framework, the Molecular Assembly (MA) methodology employs elementary geometric building shapes to recursively construct target molecules. The minimum number of shape-overlapping steps is proposed as a quantitative measure of the prebiotic selectivity required for molecular formation. However, a critical evaluation reveals significant limitations in this approach. The MA steps fail to correspond to the actual number of chemical processes involved, overlook the diverse and often unrelated reactions needed for identical shape overlaps, and disregard critical factors such as environmental conditions, thermodynamic and kinetic constraints, intermediate stability, and the necessity of isolating target molecules to prevent further reactions. Despite the ambitious scope of Assembly Theory, the methodology fails at this time to elucidate any of the abiotic chemical details required for a naturalistic origin of life.

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INTRODUCTION

Assembly Theory (AT) seems to be currently the hottest topic in theoretical biology, if not in science. Its importance was communicated by the Arizona State University that quotes Dr. Sara Walker (Caspermeyer 2023) who stated that,

With further work, this approach has the potential to transform fields from cosmology to computer science. It represents *a new frontier at the intersection* of physics, chemistry, biology and information theory. (Emphasis added)

She added (Caspermeyer 2023) that,

it's a major step toward a fundamental theory unifying inert and living matter.

Walker and Cronin emphasize that AT represents a scientific breakthrough (Caspermeyer 2023) whereby

Assembly theory provides *an entirely new way to look at the matter* that makes up our world, as defined not just by immutable particles but by the memory needed to build objects through selection over time. (Emphasis added)

Its inventor, origin-of-life researcher Lee Cronin, chemistry professor at the University of Glasgow, advertises it as the long-awaited materialistic resolution to the problem of complexity in all biological and non-biological systems. Notably,

A key feature of the theory is that it is *experimentally testable*. (Emphasis added)

Cronin adds that (Caspermeyer 2023),

This opens up the exciting possibility of using assembly theory to design new experiments that could solve the origin of life by creating living systems from scratch in the laboratory.

In 2023, the journal *Nature* propelled the theory's standing with the publication of a comprehensive overview of the main concepts (Sharma et al., 2023).

AT has generated considerable controversy, with opposing sides often claiming others have misunderstood their statements. Therefore, we will often use direct quotes to let the reader evaluate what has been stated, identifying where we have potentially misunderstood, and thereby facilitating clarifications.

Assembly Theory, a scientific breakthrough?

The claims about the theory might indeed justify the attention it has attracted. According to Walker (Caspermeyer, 2023),

Assembly theory provides a completely new lens for looking at physics, chemistry and biology as different perspectives of the same underlying reality. With this theory, we can start to close the gap between reductionist physics and Darwinian evolution; it's a major step toward a fundamental theory unifying inert and living matter.

AT proponents often claim that the theory represents a *new physics*, or *new aspect of physics*. For example (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 321) write,

AT provides a powerful interface between physics and biology. It discloses a new aspect of physics emerging at the chemical scale, whereby history and causal contingency influence what exists.

This new understanding explains how physical laws govern biological evolution (Caspermeyer 2023). According to Walker,

assembly theory, published in *Nature*, represents a major advance in our fundamental comprehension of

biological evolution and how it is *governed by the physical* laws of the universe. (Emphasis added)

The insights are said to be so profound that scientists may finally understand how to create living systems in a laboratory. In the words of the official communication by Arizona State University (Caspermeyer, 2023),

This opens up the exciting possibility of using assembly theory to design new experiments that could solve the origin of life by creating living systems from scratch in the laboratory.

In this paper we will concentrate on the most common area of application for AT, prebiotic chemistry. This parallels what AT focused on in a seminal *Nature* 2023 paper, where the authors wrote (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322),

We will discuss AT as applied to chemical systems as the main application in this manuscript because their assembly index has been experimentally measured.

Forceful objections

Discoveries of new properties of physics capable of explaining the origin of life would indeed be a dramatic development. However, many in the scientific community are expressing strong objections.

One reviewer of AT from the University of Vienna opined that the *Nature* publication is seriously flawed by unjustified exaggerations and has provoked considerable outrage among evolutionary biologists who see little if any contribution to evolutionary theory (Jaeger, 2024). In addition, established researchers of complexity theory were angered by the alleged failure of AT authors to give credit to decades of relevant previous work by others (Zenil, 2023). Zenil in particular has been very active, describing Cronin and Walker as engaging in

irresponsible self-promotion, deceitful marketing, and they claim of not contributing anything substantially new (Zenil, 2024).

Jaeger agrees with most of the criticism, noting however that (Jaeger, 2024; p. 92),

it is probably exactly the glitzy packaging that got the paper into Nature in the first place. This highlights well-known weaknesses and failures in the editorial and peer-review processes of high-profile scientific journals.

Despite his considerable misgivings, Jaeger concluded (Jaeger, 2024; p. 87),

that assembly theory has merit but is not nearly as novel or revolutionary as claimed. It certainly does not provide any new explanation of biological evolution or natural selection, or a new grounding of biology in physics.

Jaeger proposed that AT might be used to determine whether some selective force in nature is causing a fruitful path to be favored from among a multitude of unproductive alternatives, beginning from a few building blocks and rules (Jaeger, 2024).

The claims and counter-claims are surprisingly discordant for discoveries that are supposed to be *experimentally testable*.

Quantitative predictions are claimed

The theory is built on a foundational concept (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 2), namely,

AT is important because it does not require a definition of life, and instead it aims to quantify what life uniquely does. That is, life produces of [sic] complex objects in abundance.

Terrestrial organisms certainly synthesize very complex biomolecules such as DNA, RNA, and proteins, and humans also build complex objects, in many copy numbers. Unfortunately, reasonable as this *Ansatz* is,

non-terrestrial examples of this putatively unique activity of life are unavailable, which will require an examination below of what exactly is being claimed to be *experimentally testable*.

Sources of controversy are the many broad and sometimes unclear claims made about AT. For example, the theory is claimed to be capable of making predictions about future discoveries despite denying having to explain the functions of new complex objects. To illustrate (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 321), we read that

The framework of AT allows us to predict features of new discoveries during selection, and to quantify how much selection was necessary to produce observed objects.

Since evolution theory assumes progress occurs via natural processes having no long-term goal (teleology), the alleged ability of AT to predict future features raises high expectations. The claim that selection can be quantified was addressed briefly in part 1 of this series. We will critically evaluate here the key promise that the amount of guidance provided through natural processes (called selection in AT), presumably Darwinian-like but prebiotic, can be quantified in the manner proposed. According to the Nature paper (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 321),

We introduce a measure called assembly (A), capturing the degree of causation required to produce a given ensemble of objects. This approach enables us to incorporate novelty generation and selection into the physics of complex objects. It explains how these objects can be characterized through a forward dynamical process considering their assembly.

An example will help understand why skepticism is being voiced. Suppose ancient Egyptian pyramids are analyzed and it is

found that they were constructed from stone blocks. The researchers analyze various possible assembly pathways and propose a way to estimate the degree of causation that had been necessary, and publish a specific number called an assembly index. This approach would raise skeptical questions. What new physics or way of viewing physics have been discovered? What does the number mean?

The authors of AT papers recognize that the assembly processes their methodologies use must be capable of constructing relevant chemical and biological features. They pointed out that (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322),

The challenge in each case will be to construct an assembly space that has a clear physical meaning in terms of *what operations can be caused to occur* to make the object. (Emphasis added)

This is an important requirement. What are the operations involved in AT with respect to abiotic chemistry and are these derived from physics?

Review of the Molecular Assembly methodology

Is the molecular assembly (MA) concept proposed by AT a valid although indirect surrogate to infer the amount of selectivity in prebiotic chemical pathways? In the key Nature paper, the authors explain that, (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322),

To construct an assembly space for an object, one starts from elementary building blocks comprising that object and recursively joins these to form new structures, whereby, at each recursive step, the objects formed are added back to the assembly pool and are available for subsequent steps.

Referring specifically to chemical applications, they explain that (Marshall et al., 2021; p. 3),

In using bonds as the basic unit, we describe structures as bonds connected by atoms, where two bonds are joined by superimposing an atom from each.

The diagrams provided do not conform to chemical conventions or to physically possible reactions. For example, Figure 1-A seems to suggest that a molecule was formed from two simpler molecules. Figure 1-A' shows hydrogens to help recognize what per se since molecules are being implied. This helps clarify that impossible physics is being shown, since it would imply that the two carbons highlighted in yellow become superimposed, with one carbon ceasing to exist afterward. Unfortunately, in some AT publications, a straight line sometimes means a bond that will be made later and other times it represents a methyl group. The latter is always meant in the molecular structures drawn in AT publications.

The best way to interpret these kinds of AT pathway diagrams seems to be to treat them as two-dimensional shapes for which parts can be overlaid. However, since AT should have some relevance to real chemistry, Figure 1-A could be interpreted to mean that if a process would arise in nature able to add an amino group to the carbon of an imine (C=N) group then allegedly the same process could also add an amino group to any functional group as long as chemical valence rules are fulfilled, as shown in Figure 1, A-D. This is chemically wrong.¹

Figure 1. Assembly Theory allows a structural shape element to be joined in any manner that does not violate chemical valence rules. A: NH_2 is attached to an imine, $\text{C}=\text{N}$, at the carbon position (Kempes et al., 2024; fig. 1). A': A chemically incorrect interpretation of the process implied by the Assembly Theory diagram A. B: CH_3 is attached to $\text{N}=\text{N}$ (Liu et al., 2021; fig 1. Assembly step 1). C: NH_2 is attached to the carbon of a hetero-aromatic group (Liu et al., 2021; fig 1. Assembly step 6). D: NH_2 is attached to a benzene ring. E: Gabriel synthesis process to replace Cl or Br on primary alkyls by NH_2 .

Figure 2 provides an example of how according to AT the exact same pictorial shape can imply entirely different chemical processes. As illustrated in Figure 2-A, the AT reasoning seems to be that at some point an abiotic reaction occurred that causes a single bonded carbon to attach to a $\text{C}=\text{C}$ group (in this case, a methyl group, CH_3 , was attached to a benzene ring). As shown in Figure 2-B, the same chemical process, would allegedly also permit two $\text{C}=\text{C}$ groups to react together using single bonds and even form benzene. This is chemically absurd, but these incompatible reactions are shown in Liu et al., 2021.

Analyzing figure 2 from a different chemical perspective, according to a published AT assembly pathway diagram, molecule *A* was formed from *B*. The implication using AT reasoning would be that every newly

'discovered' natural processes able to add a CH_3 group to benzene ring would also allegedly be capable of polymerizing three $\text{C}=\text{C}$ groups to form benzene. This assumption in the AT methodology makes no chemical nor physical sense. Instead, different chemical processes would be necessary for the two kinds of reactions. It is incorrect that arbitrary overlapping of portions of geometric shapes represent chemical reusability for entirely different processes.

Figure 2. Assembly Theory joins elements in a manner that satisfies valence rules and element shape by superimposing as many atoms as necessary. A: One copy of the basic element (shown in blue) leads to the addition of a single-bonded carbon to an aromatic ring. B: Three copies of the same basic element (shown in blue) can produce an aromatic ring. (Taken from Liu et al., 2021; fig 6.) A': Chemical analog of step [2]. B': Transformation of step [1] into the implied chemical reactions.

The concept of AT quantification

The concern about AT assembly pathways not reflecting the number or nature of actual chemical steps necessary at each step of the process is less about the lack of chemical realism and more about whether the methodology produces in theory quantitatively meaningful predictions.

Some form of selection is assumed to favor a series of chemical reactions along the correct pathway. These are referred to as *constraints* (Liu et al., 2021; p. 1):

Assembly theory quantifies the constraints required to produce a molecule by measuring the minimum number of steps to produce the molecular graph thereof. (Emphasis added).

And in a later paper the authors explain that (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322),

An object is finite, is distinguishable, persists over time and is breakable such that the set of *constraints to construct it from elementary building blocks* is quantifiable.” (Emphasis added).

Quantification, then, refers to the minimum number of discrete steps necessary to produce complex molecules or objects, but using operations based strictly on pictorial shapes that do not represent actual chemical processes, or even correlate with the number of actual chemical steps required. The authors state that the true path that led to complex molecules abiotically might never be known but inexplicably allege that the shortest theoretical path of an infeasible pathway is a property of a molecule. They wrote that,

No matter which methods or synthetic approaches are used, there will be no shorter way than this ideal one, which makes it an *intrinsic property of a molecule* (Liu et al., 2021; p. 3)

References to intrinsic properties in AT are part of the claim that a new form of physics or

way of looking at physics has been discovered. However, as stated above, the pictorial transformations don't reflect real chemical processes, since the pathways are merely rearranging and combining of shapes. As stated above, superimposing the same shapes can require an unrelated number of chemical steps to be feasible in the real world. Therefore, it is not at all apparent what the intrinsic property is that is being referred to.

Even the claim that no shorter synthetic path would be possible is questionable. For example, the polyethylene oxide shown in Figure 3 would seemingly require a minimum of 3 steps according to AT (each of which would require multiple steps and processing to become viable chemical steps). However, the molecule can be synthesized in a single manufacturing step, as shown in Figure 3-B.

Figure 3. Comparison of the shortest Molecular Assembly (MA) pathway vs. a shorter and simpler real chemical synthesis. A: Shortest MA pathway. B: Single-pot, one-step reaction of ethylene oxide (an initiator like KOH would be used).

We will continue to examine in the rest of this paper whether the AT methodology could provide a quantitatively valid or at least reasonable surrogate for the degree of

causation (selection) for complex molecules to be synthesized abiotically.

Assembly Index, the measure of complexity of single objects

In AT, the assembly space refers to the set of possible ways an object (such as a molecule) can be constructed from a given set of elementary building blocks and some assembly rules. As mentioned above, the shortest theoretical path is used to calculate a value of MA (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 321):

For the shortest path, the assembly space captures the minimal memory, in terms of the minimal number of operations necessary to construct an observed object based on objects that could have existed in its past. (Emphasis added).

Real objects are to be used in the construction process, such as molecules.

It is important not to overlook that MA is the metric used for prebiotic chemical selection, but the methodology only calculates the minimal number of steps to change one shape into another more elaborate one. It does consider all the alternatives that could have resulted during each assembly step. For example, in figure 2, one methyl group was added to molecule 2-B to produce 2-A but this addition could have occurred at any of 6 positions (distinguishable in non-symmetric molecules instead of benzene), plus various combinations of 2 or more methyl groups added at different positions. Something must have selected the correct outcome to proceed along the pathway to produce many copies of the intended target molecule.

Once a geometrical substructure of the target object can be produced during the construction process, it is assumed to become reusable with no restrictions. In their words (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 321),

We assume that every subobject, once available, *can be used as often as needed* to generate the object. (Emphasis added).

What is reused is not physically deterministic, but contingent and guided by selection of some kind (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 321),

Assembly captures the amount of memory necessary to produce a *selected configuration* of historically *contingent objects* (Emphasis added).

The concept of memory in AT is discussed in Appendix A.

How does quantification work? According to AT, the assembly index of object i , a_i , is the minimum number of steps required to construct an object from a set of elementary building blocks, optimally reusing simpler molecules already formed along the shortest pathway (Liu et al., 2021). This is claimed to be an empirically determinable value and fundamental property of any molecule (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322).

For molecules, the assembly index can be determined experimentally.

As discussed in Part 1 of this series, this means that a_i can be estimated from correlation equations using spectroscopic data (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 13).

Assembly of ensembles, the measure of complexity of a system of objects

In AT the complexity of a system of objects is expressed by its Assembly (A) (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 321):

Assembly is a function of two quantities: the number of copies of the observed objects and the objects' assembly indices (an assembly index is the number of steps on a minimal path producing the object).

The Assembly value is intended to quantify how much selection was involved in producing a particular system of multiple components (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 321). As they explained,

We introduce the foundations of AT and its implementation to quantify the degree of selection and evolution found in a collection of objects. Assembly is a function of two quantities: the number of copies of the observed objects and the objects' assembly indices (an assembly index is the number of steps on a minimal path producing the object).

$$A = \sum_{i=1}^N e^{a_i} \left(\frac{n_i - 1}{N_T} \right) \quad (1)$$

where A is the Assembly value represented by a system of N different objects, a_i is the assembly index of object i , n_i is the number of copies of object i , e is Euler's number and N_T is the total number of objects including replicates.

The assembly indices, a_i , are the key component of A and therefore must correlate with how much guidance was in place vs. a random process for each molecule type in the system.

Is the Assembly (A) expression reasonable?

The e^a term across the N different objects expresses the intuition that the improbability of forming complex objects increases exponentially with both the complexity and variety of composing objects. However, the methodology does not consider that some objects, such as molecules, could be more or less easily formed, e.g., for kinetic, thermodynamic, and various chemical reasons. In other words, a pictorial rearrangement could look easy but the

chemical transformation could essentially be thermodynamically impossible.

The term $(n_i - 1)$ expresses that the ensemble complexity scales linearly with the copy number (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 324). Note that when $n_i = 1$, A would not increase.

What is the purpose of N_T in the denominator? They explain that (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 323),

Normalizing by the number of objects in the ensemble allows assembly to be compared between ensembles with different numbers of objects.

It is not apparent why this normalization should be done. If one system consists of more total objects than an unrelated system, why should the overall complexity be decreased (i.e., 'normalized')?

Eqn (1) can be tested by comparing two collections of objects: red blood cells (erythrocytes) and neurons (nerve cells). Red blood cells are simpler than neurons, lacking a nucleus, most organelles, and ribosomes. Without ribosomes, they cannot synthesize new proteins. Neurons are visibly more complex, having an axon, an enormous number of dendrites, and countless synapses. Neurons have far more organelles, manufacture ribosomes, thousands of kinds of proteins in large copy numbers. Neurons are composed of far more components than red blood cells and a_i values would be assigned to all of them. These considerations used in eqn. (1) predict correctly that neurons would have higher A value. However, there are far more red blood cells than neurons in our bodies, which counteracts the resulting A calculated. It is not apparent that A will always produce the right predictions.

Another example is worth considering. Suppose a healthy human cell is compared to its cancerous counterpart. The healthy version produces proteins in an ideal stoichiometry to

fulfill all its functions. The cancerous cell has defective regulatory controls and produces far more protein copies than needed. Since A correlates with copy number and variety of components (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 324) the cancerous cells could be assigned a higher A score. It is not apparent why defective processes or systems lacking regulatory controls that are ignored in the AT methodology should be defined as being more complex. This dilemma arises from neglecting functionality, as AT does. The cancerous cells eventually self-destruct. AT does not consider factors like longevity or reliability of the ensemble of objects.

Real molecules and complexes must be assembled under feasible natural conditions for life to be possible. The major purpose of AT is to explain the origin of life, and both the Assembly Index (MA in the case of molecules) and Assembly (A) are intended to be quantitative measures of the amount of selection necessary. No example systems have been provided to illustrate how A would be calculated, so we focus in this paper on the MA of only single molecules.

Abiotic synthetic pathways for molecules like ATP and polypeptides are incompatible with almost all real environments, therefore they are manufactured in laboratories under optimized conditions. To provide a quantitative measure of the (unknown) selective forces necessary to produce complex molecules the MA methodology should include the organizational effort to establish feasible conditions for every step in the pathway. Recall that AT proponents claim that the MA processes based on overlapping pictorial shapes correlate quantitatively with selection and information. In one paper they stated that (Liu et al., 2021; p. 1),

By constructing the assembly tree from molecular structures, we will be able to not only use a molecular-based route to explore the information used to

assemble the molecules found in biology but also *infer which molecules are more likely* to have shared pathways. (Emphasis added)

Selection is often replaced by the word *information* in other papers by AT authors, for example (Marshall et al., 2022; p. 2),

This means that for complex objects there is “object-assembly” information that is generated by an evolutionary system and is not just the product of laws of physics and chemistry alone.

In Appendix B we document that AT researchers seem to argue repeatedly that their methodology correlates with the abiotic assembly process molecules actually underwent. There must be at least a strong association if, for example, MA = 5 represents more selection than MA = 4.

Disconcertingly, the authors sometimes also admit that a particular assembly pathway based on joining bonds might not represent a series of feasible chemical steps at all (Liu et al., 2021; p. 3):

An assembly pathway of a molecule does not necessarily correspond to a realistic sequence of chemical reactions that produce this molecule. Instead, *the shortest assembly pathway bounds the likelihood of the molecule forming probabilistically*. (Emphasis added)

The last sentence in the quote above is misleading since the probability of a molecule forming abiotically has ignored virtually all chemical realities, as will be discussed below and in Part 3 of this series.

Unfortunately, the MA values do not calculate the probability of obtaining a desired molecule compared to all possible alternatives, as mentioned above. In addition, all interfering materials were excluded. As explained in a recent paper (Marshall et al., 2022; p. 2),

The application of assembly spaces allows us to consider paths through the space of possible objects that could be created through a model of joining through random interactions. We can find the shortest possible path to create an object, *in the context of other possible objects that could have been created at each step*, and come to a *judgement* on whether a random system (even a biased one) could have selected for a population of that object without additional information. (Emphasis added)

A *judgement* does not resemble the scientific precision mentioned above whereby “For molecules, the assembly index can be determined experimentally” (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322). In any event, the MA metric does not permit quantification of the proportion of deleterious molecules that would have formed. This can be a serious drawback if large copy numbers of correct final molecules are to result but the required basic building elements cannot have been available anymore.

The meaning of selection in AT

The proponents of AT have been strongly affected by Darwinian theory. They claim that (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 321),

Evolutionary theory explains why some things exist and others do not through the lens of selection.

Specifically (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 324),

By aiming to detect ‘selection’, we mean a process similar to selection in Darwinian evolution.

even though the chemical processes are prebiotic.

Expressing selection somewhat more generally, they propose that (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322)

First, there must be objects in its environment that can constrain the steps to assemble the object and second *these objects themselves have been selected*. (Emphasis added)

Occasionally, the authors propose hypothetical selective processes such as templating, molecular networks, or other mechanisms leading to their own replication (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 4, 27) without providing concrete examples or an explanation of why these are Darwinian-like. One reviewer noted correctly that (Ellis, 2023; p. 247),

The authors’ key contention is that a transition from no selection to selection — such as happened when inanimate matter became animate — changes the pathways taken in assembly space.

Fundamentally, AT proponents claim that there must have been some kind of non-cognizant selection, since they are materialists.

Zenil and others have voiced strong criticisms against AT (see Appendix C), claiming that it is merely another compression algorithm virtually identical to other ones developed long ago. He and others have also argued forcefully that Cronin and Walker have failed to give credit to previous work by others. Consequently, the critics state that AT offers very little that is substantially novel (Appendix D) and no justification for their hyperbolic claims.

Cronin and his team have responded to some of these criticisms. While not denying that AT is mathematically another compression algorithm and a measure of complexity, they emphasize that AT’s purpose is to calculate the minimum number of steps necessary to assemble real objects as a measure of selection (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 13, 23). In complexity theory, previously found substrings within a sequence are reused,

whereas AT is said to reuse physical repetitive subcomponents (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 27). Consequently, the geometric figures reused in MA pathways must represent real chemical processes in some manner.

The AT proponents assume that life must have arisen through natural processes. In none of their papers do they entertain the possibility of an intelligent agent being a possible source of guidance or selection. They recognized that the necessary chemicals could not have formed in large copy numbers through random processes; therefore, they concluded that some kind of *natural* selective forces must have played a decisive role.

AT authors have mentioned a distinction between biosignatures, that include objects manufactured within the bodies of organisms and also intelligently produced artifacts. For example, they

propose that objects with a high assembly index can be uniquely identified as those that must have been produced using directed biological or technological processes rather than purely random processes (Marshall et al., 2022; p. 1).

In other words, organisms can engage in intelligent activity, but intelligence must not have produced organisms. All selective forces are attributed to evolution. Human technologies are claimed to be due to evolution since allegedly humans evolved and ultimately derived from inanimate matter. The circularity of this argument is apparent.

One enthusiastic reviewer of AT, however, did not seem so comfortable with this aspect of reductionist materialism noting correctly that (Ellis, 2023; p. 248),

after intelligent action becomes possible, the kinds of assembly path that are possible change fundamentally.

To reiterate, the central claim of AT is that the combinatorial space of prebiotic molecules and genetic elements in cells is so large, that some form of selective bias must have existed to produce life (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 25). AT promises to connect the inorganic prebiotic world with the subsequent biological world (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 25). Therefore, some kind of advantage must have been provided during each of the intermediate states causing them to be selected (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 26).

DISCUSSION

Molecular Assembly (MA) corresponds to the assembly index (a_i) when applied to the manufacture of chemicals. MA values are defined as the minimum number of steps required in an assembly pathway algorithm to produce a target molecule. When comparing molecules that can be assembled beginning from the same basic elements, a higher MA value implies that more guidance ('selectivity') was necessary.

Unfortunately, the MA values capture very poorly the amount of selection necessary for prebiotic chemistry to have worked, as summarized by the multiple neglected factors shown in Table 1. Satisfying each requires some form of selection. In addition, no examples of non-volitional chemical assembly selection have been demonstrated by AT proponents. Specifically, this means examples of multiple preferred intermediates in a pathway *contra* the chemical outcomes that kinetic and thermodynamic factors would have produced.

Table 1. Factors not taken into account by Molecular Assembly (MA) algorithms to quantify theoretical pathways.

Factor No.	Factors not taken into account
	MA pathways do not capture chemical realities
1	The number of real chemical processes required during each assembly step.
2	The selection of necessary environmental conditions to make the chemical processes feasible ^{a)} .
3	Product yields based on thermodynamics and kinetics.
4	The stability of the intermediate molecules plus isolation and protection of the correct final product.
5	The effects of reagents and environmental conditions required for each assembly step on all the molecules in the pathway ^{b)} .
6	The quantitative guidance of choosing the shortest theoretical path vs. the actual one used.
7	Target molecules are prevented from further reactions
	The elementary building blocks include intelligent selection
8	The selection involved in providing all the elementary building blocks for each individual chemical pathway a priori ^{c)} .
9	The guidance provided in preventing contaminants to be found among the elementary building blocks.
10	The chemical effects of molecules used to produce the elementary building blocks on all compounds throughout the assembly pathway.
11	The chemical steps necessary to produce the elementary building blocks chosen.

a) Temperature, pH, solvent, reagents, catalysts, UV light or absence thereof, etc.

b) For example, an individual assembly step might only be chemically possible if intense UV light would create free radicals; or under very acidic conditions; or at very high temperatures; or in the presence of specific catalysts. These factors would affect all compounds in that environment.

c) Different elementary building blocks are assumed in the shortest pathways for different target molecules, preventing comparison of the resulting MA values.

Figure 4 illustrates what is meant by necessary processing details not being taken into account in the MA methodology. In this example, two wheels are ‘joined’ and seemingly lead to an ideal intermediate in merely one step. However, in a manufacturing context, this would ignore numerous details, like how the assembly lines were constructed; how the two wheels were perfectly aligned; how the interface between them produced a perfect axle; how the result was transported elsewhere, and protected from damage; etc.

Figure 4. Example of a complex assembly process that superficially requires only one assembly step. Fictitious example drawn with the help of AI.

We will discuss next two broad categories of reasons why MA values are poor quantitative measures of chemical pathway selectivity:

I. MA pathways do not capture chemical realities.

II. The elementary building blocks include intelligent selection.

The consequence is that the numerical values of MA does not seem able to illuminate anything about the yet-to-be-discovered guidance necessary for putative prebiotic chemical pathways to be feasible.

I. MA pathways do not capture chemical realities

The first reason MA values express chemical selectivity poorly is (Hazen et al., 2024; p. 2)

the disconnect between the proposed theoretical assembly pathways and actual chemical processes, and the absence of kinetic and thermodynamic factors in assessing the probability for a complex molecule’s formation.

The molecular assembly value does not correlate with the number of actual chemical processes necessary (factor no. 1 in Table 1) nor with the selective guidance provided to ensure that the necessary environmental conditions (temperature, pH, solvent, catalyst, etc.) have been suitably organized (factor no. 2 in Table 1). Recall that (Sharma et al., 2023),

In chemical systems, molecular assembly theory treats bonds as the elementary operations from which molecules are constructed.

The logic underlying the algorithms offered is that (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322),

The shortest path to build a given molecule can be found by breaking its bonds and then ordering its motifs in order of size, starting from atoms and moving to larger motifs by adding bonds in sequence.

Although the assembly steps are not stated to describe exact chemical processes, they are claimed to reflect chemical realities (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322):

The assembly measure that we have presented here both *uses realistic dynamics for molecules*, using bonds as building blocks, and is computable for any molecule. (Emphasis added)

Appendix B provides many more quotes to demonstrate that the assembly process is allegedly a quantitatively valid surrogate for real-world chemical synthesis. Our analysis in this paper fails to support this claim.

Comparison of a molecular assembly pathway with the implied chemistry

In the example shown in Figure 5 to synthesize adenine, the bonds C–C, C=C, C–N, and C=N are used as the elementary building blocks. The intermediate molecular structures formed are added to the assembly pool and assumed to be freely reusable (Liu et al., 2021; p. 1).

Figure 5. Molecular assembly pathway vs. a chemical view to manufacture adenine. A: Assembly pathway redrawn with simplifications from Liu et al., 2021, fig. 1. B: Atoms were added to clarify the chemical structures and transformations implied by the assembly pathway A.

For assembly step [1] in Figure 5, $\text{CH}_2=\text{NH}$ (methylene imine) is shown to form $\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}=\text{NH}$ (formamidine). This might be implemented via two sequential chemical reactions:

Reaction (2) would require a reagent such as a Lewis acid like AlCl_3 or BF_3 (not likely to

be available prebiotically) to activate the carbon on $\text{CH}_2=\text{NH}$ to facilitate nucleophilic attack by ammonia. A non-polar or moderately polar solvent such as THF (tetrahydrofuran) or toluene would be used (both prebiotically impossible) to dissolve the reagents under mild heating ($50\text{-}80^\circ\text{C}$) to encourage the formation of the C–N bond without causing degradation of the unstable product $\text{H}_2\text{N-CH}_2\text{-NH}_2$. This illustrates how selectivity must include providing all the indispensable environmental details (factor no. 2 in Table 1).

Reaction (3), loss of H_2 , makes no sense thermodynamically (factor no. 3 in Table 1), and in the presence of ubiquitous water $\text{H}_2\text{N-CH}_2\text{-NH}_2$ would hydrolyze instead (factor no. 4 in Table 1). Even if $\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}=\text{NH}$ (formamidine) could somehow be produced, it would hydrolyze in water and not be available for further synthetic purposes:

Continuing with assembly step [2] in Figure 5-B, the AT pathway now requires methylating of $\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}=\text{NH}$ (formamidine). We cannot offer any sensible suggestion how this could be accomplished using the molecules or bonds represented by the four elementary building blocks provided. Ignoring this restriction, two potential chemical paths can be suggested.

in the presence of a base. However, dimethyl sulfate $(\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2\text{SO}_2$ is highly unstable in the presence of water (factor no. 3 in Table 1), decomposing into methanol and sulfuric acid (the reverse of how it is usually synthesized) and therefore would not be expected to have been present abiotically. Suitable solvents such as acetone, acetonitrile, and dichloromethane are prebiotically unrealistic (factor no. 2 in Table 1).

An alternative methylation reaction would use methyl iodide

in the presence of a base. However, CH_3I would not have been present prebiotically, and dissolves poorly in water. The reaction would require suitable solvents such as acetone, acetonitrile, or tetrahydrofuran, all prebiotically unrealistic.

Assembly step [5] in Figure 5 implies that once the ability to form a carbon-carbon double bond ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) exists somewhere in nature, this reaction could be implemented whenever needed in any chemical context. This suggests that two methyl groups must first react together and then H_2 eliminated to form the six-membered ring shown. If the first step is to be executed through high energy radiation to produce free radicals, one must assume all other molecules in the environment would also be exposed both to this radiation and to the free radicals formed, destroying most of them and creating countless undesired new molecules (factor no. 5 in Table 1). Obtaining the product shown in multiple copies reliably through such a pathway would be unrealistic.

Paradoxically, occasionally the AT proponents acknowledge that chemical feasibility has not been taken into account in their assembly diagrams. In one publication they admitted that (Marshall et al., 2022; p. 13),

in our recent work on molecules, we assumed that any structure could be created by joining two others, *not considering chemical feasibility* (other than following valence rules) or modelling steps where molecules partly fall apart. What we can do, however, is *use the assembly process as a structural complexity model* (Emphasis added).

Unfortunately, this confirms Zenil's concern that AT is merely another compression algorithm. Nevertheless, AT authors insist that the hypothetical assembly pathway is a useful metric to quantify causal selection (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 16):

The assembly index, as the size of the shortest path, places a minimum bound that can be used to calculate the smallest possible amount of causation required to generate the object, allowing a lower bound that distinguishes object formation via selection as distinct from random.

This is based on viewing the assembly pathway as a measure of structural complexity, essentially the reverse of mass spectroscopy fragmentation (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 17). However, bond breaking via the ionization process (for example, using a beam of high-energy electrons) is not the reverse of how molecules are synthesized, as discussed in Part 1 and Appendix E.

Although chemical feasibility is not considered in the algorithms to construct the shortest pathway, the authors insist that AT is more than another compression algorithm and that it provides fundamental insights into how molecules could be assembled physically. One way this message is emphasized is by showing in the AT literature the final outcome of MA pathways as named molecules that are structurally entirely correct. For example, as mentioned above, a straight line extending off the ends of a target molecule always represents a $-\text{CH}_3$ group in the final molecules.

II. The elementary building blocks include intelligent selection

The second reason MA values express chemical selectivity poorly, if at all, is that the assembly logic of AT begins with a known target structure to identify the minimally

necessary elementary building blocks needed. This means that (Marshall et al., 2017; p. 4),

The choice of the basic substructures depends on the context of the desired complexity. For example, if we are establishing the complexity of the word 'banana', then *we could select* the set of unique structures {b, a, n} (Emphasis added)

This form of selection indicates intelligent foresight (factor no. 7 in Table 1). Figure 2 shows how the structure of toluene was conceptually fragmented using the AT methodology to obtain single elementary building block (—), with no consideration of chemical synthetic feasibility. The chemical shapes in Figure 2 imply that once a C=C functional group 'discovered' how to attach to a single bond, this process would be reusable in any context. The simplest chemical interpretation to form a benzene ring this way would be if three ethylene (H₂C=CH₂) groups were to polymerize after forming free radicals. However, a single carbon methyl group (-CH₃) could not be added to the benzene ring this way, using the only building block provided, C=C which has two carbon atom. (Any other chemical proposal suffers from the same dilemma: abstracting a single C from C=C would require extraordinary conditions).

The above quote then continues (Marshall et al., 2017; p. 5),

where the complexity is relative to all other words that can be made *from those three letters*. (Emphasis added)

In this example, all letters beside {b, a, n} were excluded. Otherwise, a multitude of other interfering words and word fragments could have also been generated by a random process. This intelligent guidance is also neglected in the MA algorithms (factor no. 8 in Table 1) and thus the quantitative measure of selection.

Applying this reasoning to prebiotic chemistry, many interfering reactions were prevented by judiciously restricting the elementary building blocks. For example, a major problem for OoL chemists is to find abiotic pathways for the 20 biogenic amino acid building blocks despite the vast number of substances that would interfere by reacting with potential precursors or ruin the amino acids by reacting with them once formed. The AT methodology to form all 20 amino acids would identify the necessary kinds of bonds based only on the atoms needed by amino acids {C, O, N, S, H} circumventing an intractable problem altogether. Some kind of extraordinary guidance (selection) would have been necessary to exclude all the interfering molecules for the AT methodology to have any validity.

Assembly step [1] in Figure 5 implies that CH₂=NH molecule, represented pictorially as =N, was available in nature and became incorporated in a pathway to form adenine. However, this highly reactive molecule must have arisen from preexisting chemicals. Probably the most promising precursor would have been formaldehyde (CH₂O) which could react with ammonia (NH₃). However, adding formaldehyde to the basic building blocks would be a chemical disaster, since formaldehyde and the many compounds formed from it would interfere with the subsequent steps needed to form adenine (which it would also destroy through further reactions once formed). The guidance needed to avoid these deleterious chemical reactions are mentioned as factor no. 9 in Table 1.

If MA values are to serve as a quantitative measure of complexity, able to distinguish between molecules derived from life or not, then the origin of the elementary building blocks must be accounted for in a consistent manner (factor no. 10 in Table 10). An example taken from an AT publication is shown in Figure 6 where the only elementary

building block was cyclohexane. A MA pathway for a different complex molecule that required a cyclohexane as an intermediate in its structure would begin with a set of basic elements that can create cyclohexane. However, in this literature example cyclohexane is assumed to be freely available as a primary basic building block (thereby also avoiding all interfering reactions from the other basic elementary molecules). This is a serious inconsistency in the MA methodology.

Figure 6. The Molecular Assembly algorithms begin with only the necessary elementary building blocks. Here cyclohexane was used to conceptually form all the fused rings shown. (Based on Sharma et al., 2023; fig. 1-C).

CONCLUSIONS AND FINAL COMMENTS

Assembly Theory purports to quantify the amount of selection required to form complex molecules abiotically. Chemicals with large MA values require many specific sequential steps to be assembled from simpler building blocks which implies some form of guidance or cumulative selection. However, the MA algorithms are based on pictorial operations that do not permit the minimum number of physically real processing details to be estimated. Table 1 documents many essential aspects of chemical processes that are also not represented in the MA values.

AT is claimed to be more than merely another algorithm to quantify complexity. A key insight is said to be that a series of basic elements were assembled sequentially into ever more complex objects. However, there

have been many other theories that assume complex life arose by combining simple basic elements.

The Greek philosopher Democritus, along with his teacher Leucippus, developed an early form of atomic theory around the 5th century BC. Atoms having different shapes and sizes were claimed to have combined to form all substances.

The Hypercycle Theory developed by Manfred Eigen and Peter Schuster in the 1970s (Eigen and Schuster, 1979) is also based on the idea of self-assembling into more complex structures. Simple molecules act as building blocks upon which a network of interactions leads to higher-order structures. Through ‘mutations’ and ‘selection’, more complex hypercycles were assumed to have emerged.

Darwinian evolution by natural selection is the current best-known theory of higher development being produced through a set of hierarchical intermediates.

AT is claimed to offer a new view of physics, and to answer many questions about life and evolution. Therefore, it is reasonable to expect it to provide concrete insights into real prebiotic chemical processes that go beyond the already established intuition that simpler molecules like amino acids somehow reacted to form more complex molecules like polypeptides. Our analysis casts serious doubts on whether the algorithms to assemble complex chemicals by combining geometric shapes have answered the questions AT claims to have addressed. Table 1 documents 10 factors not incorporated into the MA value, despite being fundamental problems facing OoL research. Increasing the MA value by 1 for each hypothetical assembly step might correlate with complexity of a molecule structure, but not to the processes by which it could be formed abiotically.

Since the AT proponents do not claim the proposed shortest pathways actually ever occurred, one is left with a hypothetical assembly pathway of shapes whose feasibility has not been chemically validated. Therefore, it seems disingenuous to claim that a new physics has been discovered or that a breakthrough in explaining prebiotic chemistry has been offered.

The methodology will produce the same value for an object no matter where it is found in the universe (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 16). This is implied to be a major benefit of AT, but why

should this be a merit? The fact that the same MA value is calculated even when the conditions would render the reactions *de facto* impossible suggests it is not a valid indicator for any selective factors involved on earth.

In Part 3 we analyze all possible kinds of selection and argue that the only unitary force capable of covering all cases is intelligent agency.

Appendix A. The concept of memory in Assembly Theory

Some compression algorithms used in computer science store a copy of all the substrings encountered during the compression process. If the same substring is reencountered, it can be referred to in the compressed version of the original sequence since all substrings remain in the computer's memory. Memory in AT parlance is a hypothetical record of the sequence of chemical reactions and environmental conditions for every step along the pathway that led to the final molecule. Allegedly this retained memory would guide the creation of multiple copies of the same complex molecule.

The substrings used by the computer algorithms are indeed represented by an encoding system. Therefore, software programs can be written to find the substring which matches the longest substring possible when scanning the original message. However, there is no corresponding mechanism to reestablish the same environmental conditions present elsewhere perhaps millions of years earlier to execute specific chemical reactions abiotically. An immense variety of chemical reactions can occur throughout the world, from the inner core to the exosphere, and the individual details are not encoded somewhere to be reused in a different context later.

The perennial problem in OoL chemistry is that the individual chemical reactions needed by a synthesis pathway require very specific conditions, such as pH, reagents, catalysts, temperature, solvent, UV light (or the absence thereof), and importantly, the absence of interfering chemicals that are reaction-specific. The conditions for one reaction are usually incompatible with those needed for another reaction, which is why in practice each reaction is carried out separately by chemists under carefully set up laboratory conditions.

The dilemma is known to AT proponents, who admit that (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 326),

some unconstrained prebiotic synthesis reactions, such as the formose reaction, end up producing tar, which is composed of a large number of molecules with too low a copy number to be individually identifiable.

In other words, carefully controlled conditions and separation processes would be necessary to obtain the desired chemical via the formose reaction (formaldehyde, CH_2O , catalyzed by a base and a divalent metal such as calcium). There were no convenient set of prebiotic instructions available to perform this. Tar is sticky and attracts other molecules instead of separating out the right molecule.

The assembly index (MA for molecules) is claimed to correlate with the amount of causation required to generate the target object (Kempes et al., 2024; p. 16). This requires that two correlations be significantly high.

- 1) The shortest path predicted by the MA algorithms based on geometrical shapes must correlate well with the shortest path that is chemically feasible under abiotic conditions.
- 2) The shortest chemically feasible path must correlate with the pathway that actually occurred.

It is impossible to know if condition 1) would have a correlation significantly above random since none of the chemical environmental requirements are incorporated into the MA value and the bond joining methodology cannot be correlated with real chemical reactions. To illustrate, some of the AT steps, like mixing two cyclohexane molecules to form a fused decalin ring (Figure 6), are not chemically meaningful.

To reiterate, since the actual path taken is not known, it is impossible to know if a hypothetical shortest feasible path would correlate with it in terms of the amount of causation needed.

To summarize, executing a step stored in 'memory' in AT implies that all the necessary conditions (including the molecules that are to

react) for every step along the pathway are organized whenever and available wherever needed. Prebiotic chemistry, however, is supposed to be guided by natural processes and no such purposeful guidance has been stored anywhere.

Appendix B. Molecular assembly pathways claimed to describe real processes

Cronin, Walker, and their co-workers claim that the molecular assembly process provides important insights into real pre-biotic chemistry. They write, for example, (Slocombe and Walker, 2024; p. 949) that,

the team leveraged principles from the recently developed theory of molecular assembly (MA) and related ideas to define a rigorous concept of a scale for complexity, connected to a theory *for how evolution builds complex molecules*. (Emphasis added)

How complex molecules are built implies physically real processes.

As another example (Slocombe and Walker, 2024; p. 949) state that,

AT can be used to study directed vs undirected processes *in the creation of molecules* (Emphasis added).

In a seminal paper, writing in the context of prebiotic chemistry the authors explained (Marshall et al., 2017; p. 4) that,

The Pathway Complexity is calculated in the context of any possible objects that *could be constructed* from the same subunits. (Emphasis added).

The inescapable conclusion based on quotes like these is that the subunits shown as geometric shapes represent molecular structures from which complex chemicals ('objects') can actually be constructed. Quotes like the following demonstrate that the intention is to model chemical synthesis (Marshall et al., 2017; p. 4):

Pathway Complexity bounds the likelihood of natural occurrence by *modeling a naive synthesis* of the object from populations of its basic parts, where at any time pairs of existing objects can join in a single step. (Emphasis added)

All scientific models are intended to represent something real to some level of detail.

Pathway Complexity, also called Molecular Assembly, is intended to provide a quantitative measure of selection necessary to produce complex chemicals using physically possible operations, as expressed in the following quote (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322):

The aim of AT is to develop a new understanding of the evolution of complex matter that naturally accounts for selection and history in terms of what *operations are physically possible* in constructing an object.

Clearly, the only physically possible operations to construct chemicals are real chemical processes. The operation of superimposing parts of two cyclohexane molecules to form a fused ring (Figure 6) must therefore be understood as a claim that this is a physically possible operation.

The chemical pathways offered by AT proponents are said to be reusable (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 326) since,

Once a pathway to build an object is discovered, the object can be reproduced if the mechanism in its environment is selected to build it again.

The authors do reuse parts of pathways, and entire pathways to produce many copies. One can only reuse something that exists.

The authors of AT papers realized that to be quantitatively relevant as a measure of selection, the molecular assembly methodology must describe (or directly correlate with) physically meaningful chemical processes.

AT authors criticize how other researchers invoke natural selection quantitatively by saying they, "just describe outcomes and do not relate to the *underlying physics*." (Ellis,

2023; p. 247. Emphasis added). AT is supposed to be different, since,

Assembly theory fills this gap in an innovative way by quantifying the degree of evolution and selection in an ensemble of objects. (Ellis, 2023; p. 247)

It would be meaningless to claim that the *underlying physics* is being addressed without implying that real chemistry is implied.

Later in the same review the 'theory of the adjacent possible' was also criticized on the basis of not being founded on actual physics (Ellis, 2023; p. 248):

But, similarly to those earlier attempts to quantify evolution, this description

does not relate to the *underlying physics*. (Emphasis added)

The hypothesized selective processes were not elaborated on, but the authors insisted that they could only be material causes that lacked any purpose. They write, for example (Marshall et al., 2022; p. 2),

Thus, we remove the requirement for an external imposition of meaning.

This seems to contradict the implication of teleology expressed elsewhere, such as the claim (Ellis, 2023; p. 248) that,

the structure of the heart comes from genes that were selected to produce that structure.

Appendix C. Is AT merely another compression algorithm?

Zenil and his co-workers have voiced strong concerns about AT. They note that AT proponents illustrate how their algorithms work by compressing example strings such as ABRACADABRA and BANANA. These are favorite examples to teach LZ77, LZ78, or LZW compression algorithms in computer science courses (Abrahão et al., 2024; p. 11).

The critics view AT as being subsumed within Algorithmic Information Theory (AIT), which has already been applied successfully to detect, identify, cluster, and classify / distinguish organic from non-organic molecules (Zenil et al., 2018). AIT algorithms such as the LZ family have already been used effectively in many fields including chemistry (Zenil et al., 2018), biology (Zenil et al., 2012, 2018; Hernández-Orozco et al., 2018; Zenil, 2013), and medicine (Zenil et al., 2018; Li et al., 2003; Dauwels, et al., 2011; Abrahão et al., 2024). Like AT, these earlier studies also used compression techniques to interpret evolutionary theory (Hernández-Orozco et al., 2018; Zenil et al., 2019b), technosignatures (Zenil et al., 2012; Zenil et al., 2023a), and explorations into causality (Zenil et al., 2019a, Zenil et al., 2023b).

AT introduces a cutoff value for MA to demarcate between organic and non-organic molecules, but similar cutoff values have already been derived in other studies (Uthamacumaran et al., 2022; Zenil et al., 2018).

In the MA algorithms, more complex chemical features are pictorially derived from simpler ones, and the critics point out that AT assumes that this directionality in time is conflated with how an object was chemically assembled, starting from its static, instantaneous configuration (Abrahão et al., 2024; p. 5). To expand on this objection, in mass spectroscopy the same fragment (for example CH_3^+) can often be obtained multiple times from different parts of a molecule. This does not imply that individual CH_3 groups had been added to different parts to produce the molecule, nor does the presence of such fragments communicate anything about the order of chemical steps.

Instead of setting a lower bound for the minimum number of chemical processing steps, the assembly index can be more naturally viewed as an approximation to the number of factors used in a traditional LZ compression scheme, such as LZ78 or LZW (Abrahão et al., 2024; p. 2).

Zenil's group has argued that the AT assemble process is equivalent to a Context-Free Grammar (CFG), and the assembly index value is analogous to the size of the compressing grammar (Abrahão et al., 2024; p. 2). They conclude that AT has contributed very little that is novel to the fields of compression, complexity, or origin of life.

Appendix D. Earlier work not given credit by AT authors

In 2018, Zenil's team reported before Cronin and Walker that organic and nonorganic compounds could be distinguished using compression algorithms based on InChi molecular descriptions and molecular distance matrices. These representations of molecules contain the same kind of information as the spectral data used by AT (Zenil et al., 2018). The algorithm developed (Zenil et al., 2018) was based on the Block Decomposition Method introduced in the mid-2010s. In this work, the structures of 158,399 molecules were extracted from the ChemicalData database and distributed among 32 partially overlapping categories such as hydrocarbons, drugs, biomolecules, inorganics, organics, etc.

The authors were commendably modest about the potential use of their results, writing (Zenil et al., 2018; p. 6),

Our approach may find some applications. For example, one may find that low algorithmic complexity molecules are easier to synthesize or to assemble into larger new molecules and drugs because high algorithmic complexity molecules would share fewer physical properties.

Noteworthy is that the authors did not claim any link between molecular complexity as

they defined it and feasibility of prebiotic synthesis.

In the 2018 paper Zenil and co-workers validated their results against a complete molecular database having more than 15,000 compounds and compared their results with other mathematical approaches (Zenil et al., 2018). Although this work was well-known to Cronin and Walker since there had been active communication between the groups, this was not acknowledged in the seminal Nature publications by Cronin and his team (Zenil, 2023).

Zenil and his colleagues insist that AT is a variant of general principles used for decades in standard dictionary-based compression algorithms like run-length encoding (RLE), Huffman and Lempev-Ziv (LZ)-based (Uthamacumaran et al., 2024). (The use of a dictionary of construction elements by software algorithms is the basis for the term 'memory' in AT.) Using the same mass spectra dataset as Cronin's team, Zenil et al. showed that the numerical indices using these algorithms correlate very strongly with the MA results based on AT, so that assuming a time-ordered assembly pathway as AT offers no advantages nor insights (Uthamacumaran et al., 2024)

Appendix E. Molecular assembly fragments were inspired by mass spectroscopy

The historical and conceptual background of AT were reviewed in Part 1 of this series. There is a close connection between mass spectroscopy (MS) fragmentation and the assembly steps in AT. The pathway steps shown in Figures 1–3 show how they are the reverse of MA fragmentation.

It is claimed (Sharma et al., 2023; p. 322) that,

mass spectrometry can be used to measure assembly for molecules, because it can measure how molecules are *built by making bonds*. (Emphasis added)

Other papers make similar claims (Marshall, et al., 2021). With MS, most bonds can be broken, leading to many fragments. The parent fragments can often be deduced by analyzing the smaller fragments formed. Individual smaller fragments, like a methyl group, can often be produced many ways, reminiscent of how the same substring might appear in multiple parts of sequence of symbols. Superficially, reconstructing the original molecule resembles synthesizing it. However, MS fragmentation through high energy ionization is not the reverse of molecule synthesis and reconstructing the parent molecule from basic fragments does not reflect how the parent molecule was produced.

When forming a fragment, the first step in MS is ionization, where an electron is lost from the parent molecule. The electron is typically extracted from wherever the resulting cation will be most stable, such as from a site near heteroatoms or π -bonds. This creates a positively charged radical cation, $M^{+\cdot}$ of the parent molecule. The cation is unstable and fragments in different positions.

The molecule often breaks in a way that produces the most cation fragments at one end and a free radical species at the other end.

Consider a simple example using acetone (CH_3COCH_3) as the parent molecule:

Major fragmentation products:

Minor products (also after rearrangements) can also form:

However, the reverse process does not represent a realistic synthetic route. Process (8) is the major outcome, but the reverse synthesis step, CH_3CO^+ joining with $\cdot\text{CH}_3$ to form CH_3COCH_3 only makes sense as a free radical reaction:

The few times MA steps shown in the AT pathways could be implemented in one step imply free radical chemistry, but high-energy environments forming indiscriminate free radicals would devastate the biomolecules needed for life.

Glossary of key terms used in Assembly Theory

Assembly Contingent (AC) Assembly Contingent is a subset of Assembly Possible. AC represents the possible space of objects which could be built where one or more subassemblies are assumed must have been used.

Assembly index The number of steps on the shortest pathway able to produce an object.

Assembly Observed (AO) An observed object is broken down recursively to generate a set of elementary building unit that can be used to then recursively construct different assembly pathways to the original object.

Assembly Pool Set of possible structures at a given assembly step that were formed previously and are available at the next assembly step to create higher-order structures.

Assembly possible (AP) The space of physically possible objects, which can be generated by combinatorial expansion from a defined set of elementary building blocks, using all physical rules of object construction at every step.

Assembly space All recursively assembled pathways that produce a specific object.

Assembly Universe (AU) All possible pathways for assembling any object composed of the same set elementary building blocks as our target object.

Discovery Timescale (τ_D) The time scale required by the assembly process to explore the potential combinatorial space of the objects present in the assembly pool toward creating novel unique objects.

Production Timescale (τ_P) Is usually specific to a given object and generates copies at the production rate.

Rate of Discovery How it takes for nature to discover a manufacturing process for a molecule.

Rate of Production (kp) How rapidly a specific object is manufactured after the process was discovered.

Acknowledgements. We are very grateful for helpful discussions with Dr. Onsi Fakhouri, Dr. Hector Zenil, Dr. James Tour, Salvador Cordova, and numerous engineers from the Intelligent Design movement.

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¹For example, the addition of -NH_2 to *primary alkyls* can be carried out via the Gabriel synthesis (a prebiotically unrealistic pathway), whereas for *tertiary alkyl halides* steric hindrance around the tertiary carbon makes nucleophilic substitution very difficult. Instead, alkenes result through E_2 elimination, the wrong product. Gabriel synthesis is also unsuitable to add NH_2 to aromatic rings (see Figure 1-E), given the higher bond dissociation energy of the halide bonds to the sp^2 carbons.